

Flavonoid glycosides from *Myrica esculenta* leaves

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Abstract : Two flavonoid glycosides identified as flavone 4'-hydroxy-3',5,5'-trimethoxy-7-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-rhamnopyranoside (1) and flavone 3',4'-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-7-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside (2) with three known compounds β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucopyranoside and quercetin have been isolated from the leaves of *Myrica esculenta*. Their structures were elucidated on the basis of spectroscopic evidences and chemical studies.

Keywords : *Myrica esculenta*, flavonoid glycosides.

Introduction

Myrica esculenta of family Myricaceae, is an ever-green tree and useful remedy in fever, catarrh of the mucous membrane, asthma, diarrhoea and bronchitis¹. Several flavonoids^{2,3}, terpenes⁴ and tannins⁵ have been reported from different species of this plant. The paper reports isolation, structure elucidation of two flavonoid glycosides 1 and 2 along with three known compounds, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucopyranoside and quercetin from the leaves of the plant. This is first phytochemical report from leaves of the plant.

Results and discussion

Compound 1 was isolated as yellow crystalline solid (m.p. 215 °C) and responded positively in the test of flavonoid glycoside. Its molecular formula was determined as C₃₁H₃₆O₁₆ (MW 664) by FAB-MS (+ve). UV spectra showed bands at λ_{\max} (MeOH) 259, 295 and 387 nm; IR spectrum (KBr) displayed absorption bands for hydroxyl (ν_{\max} 3320 cm⁻¹) and carbonyl (ν_{\max} 1640 cm⁻¹) functions. ¹H NMR spectra furnished two singlets at δ 7.69 and 7.08 and two doublets at δ 6.93 (1H) and 6.20 (1H) of coupling constant 2.1 Hz showed a tetra substituted and tri substituted benzene rings⁶. Three sharp singlets at δ 2.50, 2.40 and 2.73 assigned for three methoxy function in the molecule. A doublet at δ 5.32 (*J* 6.8 Hz) was assignable for anomeric proton, whereas singlet at δ 0.85

(3H) showed presence of a deoxyhexose methyl. The sugars in 1 identified as α -linked rhamnose and β -linked glucose at C-7. The ¹³C NMR showed downfield peaks at δ 163.5 (C-5), 165.7 (C-7), 159.3 (C-3'), 149.5 (C-4') and 158.5 (C-5') indicating substitution at these positions. On acid hydrolysis with 10% methanolic HCl afforded 7,4'-dihydroxy-5,3',5'-trimethoxy flavone as aglycone along with glucose and rhamnose (PC, rf).

Compound 2 was isolated as yellowish crystals, molecular formula C₂₂H₂₆O₁₀ (MW 450) from its FAB-MS (+ve); UV λ_{\max} at 270, 307 nm (MeOH), 276, 428 nm (MeOH + AlCl₃); IR λ_{\max} (KBr) 1430, 1525, 1600, 3410 cm⁻¹ and FAB-MS (+ve) *m/z* 307 [M + 3H-146]⁺ data indicated the flavonoid glycoside nature. In ¹H NMR spectra the chemical shifts at δ 6.06 (d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-3), 7.7 (s, H-5), 7.1 (d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-5'), 6.9 (d, *J* 3.2 Hz, H-6') and 6.38 (s, H-2') were assigned to flavonoid protons. A singlet at δ 2.16 (3H) was assignable for OCH₃ and downfield singlet at δ 1.27 indicated hexose methyl. A doublet at δ 4.2 (*J* 2.4 Hz) indicate α -configuration of sugar. The presence of sugar was further supported by FAB-MS peaks at *m/z* 307 (100%). The ¹³C NMR showed downfield signal at δ 179.6 for C-4 (keto group), 163.4 (C-6), 159.6 (C-4'), 158.0 (C-3') and 165.8 (C-7) supporting substitution at these positions. Acid hydrolysis (10% MeOH-HCl, 10 ml, 60–80 °C, 8 h) furnished 3',4',7-trihydroxy, 6-methoxy flavone⁶ and rhamnose.

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	R ₆
1	OCH ₃	H	β-D-glucopyranosyl- (1-4)-α-L-rhamnopyranoside	OCH ₃	OH	OCH ₃
2	H	OCH ₃	α-L-rhamnopyranoside	OH	OH	H

Experimental

The leaves were collected from Nagnath Pokhari, Chamoli, Uttarakhand and identified from Ethnobotanical Laboratory, Department of Botany, H. N. B. Garhwal University, Srinagar where Boucher specimen deposited. Melting points were recorded on a Perfit melting point apparatus. ¹H and ¹³C NMR were recorded on Nicolet NT 300 Bruker spectrometer equipped with 5 mm ¹H and ¹³C probes operating at 300 and 75 MHz respectively, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer. EI-MS and FAB-MS were recorded on a JEOL X102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer. All chemical shift were referenced to internal TMS and coupling constant (*J*) in Hz. Plant extract was column chromatographed on silica gel (Qualigen, 60–120 mesh), using CHCl₃-MeOH as eluting solvents.

Extraction and isolation :

The air dried leaves (2.0 kg) were crushed into small pieces and successively extracted with *n*-hexane, CHCl₃ and MeOH separately. CHCl₃ extract on column chromatography over silica gel using CHCl₃-EtOAc as eluting solvent afforded three known compounds, β-sitosterol, β-sitosterol-β-D-glucopyranoside and quercetin. MeOH extract on repeated column chromatography over silica gel using CHCl₃-MeOH as eluting solvent with increasing concentration of MeOH afforded compounds 1 and 2.

Flavone 4'-hydroxy-3',5,5'-trimethoxy-7-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→4)-α-L-rhamnopyranoside (1) :

Yellow colored crystalline solid; UV λ_{max} (MeOH) 259, 287, 295 nm; IR ν_{max} (KBr) 1640, 3320 cm⁻¹; FAB-MS (*m/z*) : 664 [M+H]⁺, 356 [M-(146 + 162)], 324 [356-OCH₃]⁺, 307 [324-OH]⁺, 232 [307-2OCH₃]⁺; (DMSO, 300 MHz, δ ppm) 0.85 (3H, s, rhamnose CH₃), 2.50 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.40 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.73 (3H, s,

OCH₃), 3.34–4.26 (sugar protons), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-8), 7.69 (4H, s, H-6), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-3), 7.08 (2H, s, H-2', H-6'), 5.32 (d, *J* 6.7 Hz, 1''-glucose); ¹³C NMR (CD₃OD, 75 MHz, δ ppm) 136.8 (C-2), 105.8 (C-3), 179.6 (C-4), 163.5 (C-5), 99.8 (C-6), 165.7 (C-7), 94.0 (C-8), 158.5 (C-9), 105.0 (C-10), 122.9 (C-1'), 116.3 (C-2'), 159.3 (C-3'), 149.5 (C-4'), 158.5 (C-5'), 117.0 (C-6'), 56.0 (OCH₃), 61.0 (OCH₃), 51.0 (OCH₃), 103.0 (C-1''), 71.2 (C-2''), 71.9 (C-3''), 73.2 (C-4''), 70.1 (C-5''), 18.6 (C-6''), 103.1 (C-1'''), 74.5 (C-2'''), 71.9 (C-3'''), 73.1 (C-4'''), 77.0 (C-5'''), 61.9 (C-6''').

Flavone 3',4'-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-7-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside (2) :

Yellowish crystals; UV λ_{max} (MeOH) 270, 276, 307, 428 nm; IR ν_{max} (KBr) 1430, 1600, 1650, 3410 cm⁻¹; FAB-MS (*m/z*) : 489 [M+K]⁺, 450 [M]⁺, 307 [M+3H-146]⁺, 289 [M+3H-(146+H₂O)]⁺, 273 [M+3H-(146+2H₂O)]⁺, 242 [M-(146+2OH+OCH₃)]⁺; ¹H NMR (C₅D₅N, 300 MHz) δ 6.06 (1H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-3), 7.7 (1H, s, H-5), 7.1 (1H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-5'), 6.9 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, H-6'), 6.38 (1H, s, H-2'), 1.27 (3H, s, H-1'), 2.16 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.2 (1H, s, H-1''); ¹³C NMR (CD₃OD, 75 MHz) δ 146.3 (C-2), 106.2 (C-3), 179.6 (C-4), 122.0 (C-5), 163.4 (C-6), 165.8 (C-7), 94.0 (C-8), 148.9 (C-9), 105.0 (C-10), 121 (C-1'), 116 (C-2'), 158 (C-3'), 159.6 (C-4'), 116.3 (C-5'), 116.9 (C-6'), 53.7 (OCH₃), 103 (C-1''), 72.0 (C-2''), 71.9 (C-3''), 73.2 (C-4''), 70.1 (C-5''), 17.6 (C-6'').

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